

A study on the cause of difficulties in English reading skills experienced by first-year English-majored at HUFU

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Abstract

Reading in learning English as well as any language has the same benefits: Through reading, readers are developed intellectually and knowledge. Specifically, about intellectually: giving rise to ideas and reasoning. About knowledge: help to better understand people, society, and the world. It also helps the reader to improve the target language of writing, sentence structure, and word usage. Besides, the reading material provides readers with a topic to discuss, encourages engaging in communication, and contributes to creating an exciting learning atmosphere. Our collective social knowledge is limited because we have not yet built up a reading culture in the home, school, and society. Meanwhile, to have good English listening, speaking, and writing skills, we need an extensive understanding of cultural, social, economic, and political issues.

Keywords: Reading skills, Learning English, Difficulties.

1. Introduction

Reading is one of the four most essential skills for an English learner. Reading is the bridge that brings people to a world of information and knowledge through books, newspapers, etc. It helps readers discover the right words and grammatical structures and enriches their ability to communicate. Many foreign language learners now consider reading as an essential skill in learning English. First, reading is an indispensable communication skill in a civilized society. Secondly, reading English well helps them discover the vast treasure of knowledge of the world. The specialized documents, in-depth knowledge written by the great researchers and scientists in the world. At present, universities in Vietnam in general and HUFU in particular, have focused on teaching English.

Reading is a skill that will help readers develop their ability to perceive language. They help them detect and remember a lot of grammatical structures and vocabulary. After that, their brains can imitate, and they can speak out what they think about correctly, both using words and grammar. If they read a lot, paying particular attention to commonly used words, they will soon be able to apply new concepts or new structures to speaking and writing. Not only that, but it also helps them develop their intuition when learning the language. They will begin to feel which sentences are right, which ones seem to be wrong - just like they can do with their native language. Learning a

language by reading seems to take more time, other than learning based on grammar rules.

According to Bedir (1998), if teachers teach students how to learn rote regularly, students will gradually follow the path without thinking. Therefore, teachers not only focus on language development but also need to teach students how to read practically.

Rivas (1999: 12-21) notes that language problems seem to be the most frequent source of reading increasingly confronted by EFL learners at the intermediate level. Thus, we must focus on reading skills as well as language problems.

For students, read is an essential skill when you study English. Reading practice helps them learn a lot of things. The reading process helps them consolidate grammar, learn new expressions, new phrases, new structures, and expand their vocabulary. The more they read, the more likely they are to develop other skills. But in the process of learning to read English, first-year students majoring in English at HUFU encountered some difficulties. The author chooses the topic "*A study on the cause of enriching in English reading skills experienced by first-year student English-majored at HUFU*," hoping to point out those difficulties, thereby taking measures to overcome the challenges and help students improve their reading skills.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Definition of reading

Reading is a complex "cognitive" process of decoding symbols to create meaning. Reading is a way of acquiring languages, communicating and sharing information and ideas. Like languages, it is a complex interaction between documents and readers shaped by the reader's knowledge, experience, attitudes, and linguistic community, which depend on the specific culture and society. The reading process requires constant practice, development, and refining. In addition, reading requires creativity and commentary analysis. Literary readers often sink into the content of the work, in other words, converting the language into images that simulate the places in which literature has been described. Because reading is such a complex process, it cannot be controlled or defined by simple explanations. There are no specific rules on reading, but reading has allowed readers an outlet to create their own inner works. This promotes in-depth exploration of documents in the process of explaining vocabulary. Readers use many ways of readings to assist with decoding (translating symbols into sounds or creating images for spoken content) and to understand. Readers can use contextual clues to determine the meaning of unknown words. Readers can integrate the words they have read into their current thinking frame or thinking schema.

According to Diane Henry Leipzig (2001) reading is a process of many steps of word recognition, comprehension, reading fluency and motivation.

According to Nunan (1991), reading is essentially a process of deciphering a series of characters and symbols from the documents into their equivalent meaning in order to understand the meaning of the whole document.

According to Rohit, Valand (2011) reading is a complex process. Readers create sense for documents from words in the documents through their knowledge and experience. During the reading process, they constantly make predictions about what will happen next. It is this interaction with the documents that allows the reader to understand what they are reading.

Reading is defined as an interactive process between the reader and the writer. In which the reader must understand the message intended to convey the paragraph to decode it. Moreover, it is a dynamic process in which information from the documents and knowledge the reader owns interactively to enable us to build meaning before, during and after reading. In this respect, Dubin (1982: 125) argues that the task of reading is a complex skill that contains a number of psychological, physical and social factors.

2.2 Types of reading skills

2.2.1 Intensive reading

Intensive reading is the complete decoding of a document, with the goal of acquiring as much sense from it as possible. This is done by taking a document and systematically searching for each word, phrase or sequencing that you don't understand.

This is an activity that requires intense mental effort and high concentration. Because of this, learners participating in intensive reading must carefully follow specific instructions, without the risk of boredom and exhaustion. Specifically, if you want to read an intensive document, you have to carefully read interesting and concise documents, only read for a short period of time and do so when you have the most mental energy.

Intensive reading focuses on following a shorter document, doing exercises with it and learning it in detail. Following this approach, it helps language learners truly understand linguistic grammar and syntax.

According to Nuttall (1982: 23), reading lessons was primarily aimed at training students for effective reading strategies.

According to Long and Richards (1987), the intensive reading is a detailed analysis of each point about vocabulary and grammar in order to deepen the sense of document.

Palmer (1964) argued that learners focused on using dictionaries to analyze, compare and translate the meaning of document while reading. From there shows the use of dictionaries helps learners make progress in language learning.

2.2.2 Extensive reading

Extended reading is that learners are only encouraged to read documents at a level lower than their language ability, should only be on average from two new words per page, so learners can read with large amount of documents in no time limit. In this method of reading, learners can read just for fun or reading to understand the overall content of the readings and usually don't have comprehension exercises at the end of

the lesson. Therefore, the practical activity for this type of reading is usually to write a diary to record the sentences and words in the reading that they feel interesting or write about their thoughts on the content of the reading. It is the difference in purpose and activity that makes reading documents in an expanded reading diverse in categories and grades.

Talk about the role of extended reading, Nuttall (1996) in "Teaching reading skills in a foreign language" identified it as one of the two best ways, after living with native speakers, to enrich their knowledge and develop the ability to use a foreign language. Extended reading not only helps learners enrich their vocabulary, improve their reading speed but also helps to strengthen their grammar, develop their writing skills, and form reading habits for learners. This is also the conclusion of many study works in the world, including: Bamford and Day (2004) in "Extensive Reading Activities for Teaching Language" showed that extended reading helps readers improve their reading speed markedly by reading a large number of reading materials at a simple level (under their language level). More importantly, extended reading can help readers form reading habits. Al-Homoud, F., & Schmitt, N. (2009) in "Extensive Reading in a Challenging Environment" compared the two methods of reading in-depth analysis and extended reading. According to them, reading in-depth analysis is a traditional method and it is not really reading, it is just a lesson to read in class. Because in reading in-depth analysis, the reading includes a series of reading comprehension questions used as a tool to test language skills rather than reading exercises. However, Bamford and Day suggest that a combination of both reading in-depth analysis and extended reading methods should be combined. Because, for students who need to be able to analyze language and reading skills, deep reading is essential, while extensive reading can help form reading habits. This is also essential for all learners, especially students.

2.3 Difficulties in learning the reading skills

2.3.1. Decoding difficulties

Decoding is the primary skill to reading, which involves separating the sounds of words and combining sounds together. It requires the reader to have a good knowledge of the relation of the written sounds as well as the ability to apply that knowledge to successfully identify the words being written and make sense of the document.

According to Klinger (2011) a difficulty in decoding is as follows: the first is having trouble pronouncing and recognizing the meaning of the word, the second is being confused between words and sounds that other people say, the third is slow reading speed (reading each word), the fourth reading without emotional expression. Finally, do not interested in punctuation when reading.

To read well, readers need good decoding skills. Decoding skills help learners find out most of the words they have ever heard but never seen as a document as well as sound out words they are not familiar with.

All other reading skills such as, comprehension skill, reading fluency, vocabulary ... are built on the foundation of decoding skills.

2.3.2. Retention difficulties

Retention is a difficult task for learners to read. It requires both decoding skills and understanding what is written in the readings. The task of retention is formed based on the memory and ability to team and retrieve related ideas from the reader. The more and more readers read, the ability to read on a higher raise, the more they will be able to retentive what they have read.

According to David (2007) difficulties of retention include: Difficult to retentive or summarize what is read, difficult to connect what is read with previous knowledge, difficult to apply the content of a document to personal experience.

2.3.3 Comprehension difficulties

Comprehension studies show that EFL learners face some comprehension difficulties when they read. Vocabulary is the biggest difficulty for students in comprehension. One of the difficulties is that the learners has difficulty with words with similar morphologies but with different meanings, such as the word "boss" and word "bus", or word "cat" and word "cut".

Another major difficulty is the cultural difference in word usage between mother tongue and second language, thus the usage of idioms and proverbs is also different. Therefore, the reader is hard to fully understand the true meaning of the words of idioms and proverbs that they really want to convey but only understand them by translating word-by-word.

According to Farshad Farzami (2016: 10), some difficulties in comprehension the meaning of the readings include: confusion about the meaning of words and sentences, inability to connect the ideas the author wants to convey in a passage, omitting details, failing to distinguish important information and supplementary information in the readings, and ultimately lacking focus when reading.

3. Method

3.1 Aim of the study

The author of this study aims to identify the main causes of difficulty in learning to read of first-year English language students at HUFU. Since then propose some solutions to overcome those difficulties, help students improve reading skills.

3.2 Research question

To achieve the study purpose, the author will focus on answering the following two research questions:

What are the difficulties in learning to read by first-year English language students at HUFU?

What is the solution for first-year English language students at HUFİ to overcome reading difficulties?

3.3 Scope of the study

Reading skills cover a wide range of aspects, but this study focuses only on finding the causes of the first-year students' reading difficulties in English language at HUFİ and suggests a number of solutions to help students overcome difficulties and perfect their reading skills.

3.4 Method of the study

This study applied quantitative methods as method of the study. Analytical information is collected through questionnaires.

The questionnaire was sent to the first-year English language students at HUFİ in the hope of finding the difficulties they were facing during their learning to read.

3.5 Participants

The survey participants included 30 first-year students majoring in English at HUFİ, all participants were between the ages of 18 and 23 years old and had time to study English over 7 years. They are all people who have a basic English background and are using English as a second language. After completing the survey, we will better understand the difficulties they encounter in the process of learning to read English.

3.6 Instrument

In this research, the writer uses the survey tool to collect data in quantitative form. The questionnaire is considered to be the easiest information gathering tool to summarize, analyze and identify the reading skills difficulties of the survey participants.

The questionnaire is designed with 10 different questions, including two main factors that are individual learners and environmental factors that make it difficult for learners to read. Questions 1 to 6 aim to collect difficult causes that come from learners. Meanwhile, sentences 7 to 10 are designed by the writer to find contextual and environmental factors that make it difficult for students to learning reading.

3.7 Data collection procedure

Step 1: Hand out the questionnaire to students

To collect service data, the writer distributed 30 questionnaires to 30 first-year students majoring in English language at HUFİ. Students have 15 minutes to complete answering questions in the questionnaire. All responses of the survey participants are kept confidential and only serve the purpose of data analysis of the research.

Step 2: Processing collected data

The data collected from the questionnaire was processed by the writer using descriptive statistics to find out the percentage of each factor that causes difficulty in students' reading skills.

Step 3: Propose solutions to students

Based on the findings obtained from analyzing survey data, the writer will suggest some solutions to help teachers teach reading to find appropriate teaching methods to help students learn reading skills better, and students can improve their reading skills.

4. Data analysis

4.1 Data analysis comes from a learner factors

** Question 1: According to you, what do you think about your level of reading English?*

Figure 6. Level of reading English

The pie chart above shows that the reading level of students participating in the survey is quite different. Some students rate their English reading at intermediate level (10%), above intermediate level (3%) and advanced level 3%. More than half of the survey respondents wrote that their reading skills were just basic (54%), and 30% of the respondents said that their reading level was only intermediate level. The above results clearly show that limited English reading ability is one of their difficulties in learning to read.

** Question 2: How much time do you spend daily reading English?*

Figure 7. How much time do you spend daily reading English?

From the pie chart, it is shown that students don't seem to pay too much attention to learning English daily. Most students who took the survey only spent 30 minutes reading English every day. The number of students who spend 1 hour a day learning to read English is only 13.33%, 2 hours is 13.33%. Spending too little time on learning has a profound effect on student reading skills.

* Question 3: Do you have a habit of learning new words to complete reading homework after each reading lesson in class?

Figure 8: Do you have a habit of learning new words to complete reading homework after each reading lesson in class?

Many people think that forming a habit of learning new words and completing a home reading lesson right after each lesson is great for practicing reading skills. The pie chart above illustrates how often this happens. The number of hardworking students who

always learn new words and complete homework reading is very small (3.33%). While up to 60% of students participating in the survey, they sometimes learn new words and practice reading. Up to 13.33% of them never do this and 13.33% rarely do it. This sad figure reflects one of the reasons for difficulty in reading skills because the limited vocabulary will make it impossible for readers to understand the content in the document.

* *Question 4: Do you feel confident communicating with foreigners with your current vocabulary?*

Figure 9: Do you feel confident communicating with foreigners with your current vocabulary?

As the chart above shows, 67% of the respondents chose answer “no”. The vast majority of them are afraid to communicate with native speakers. They feel awkward and embarrassed when meeting foreigners because they are afraid that their English vocabulary is not enough to express the content they want to say and the incorrect pronunciation leads to misunderstandings. Obviously, students who are not confident in communication skills with foreigners are also a problem in learning to read.

* *Question 5: Do you apply reading strategies to cope with reading texts in class and at home?*

Figure 10. Do you apply reading strategies to cope with reading texts in class and at home?

The chart above shows how often reading strategies are used to cope with reading readings given in class and at home. Only 6.67% of students always apply it and is similar to the number of students who never do this. 56.67% said they only occasionally implemented the application of this reading strategy. There is 10% of regular use and 20% of students rarely do. Students who rarely or never practice a reading strategy often face many problems in the process of reading document in English such as reading and trying to translate word-by-word makes them unable to comprehend the reading document, paying attention to small details leads to missed main ideas, wasting time, psychology is afraid to read because of long reading and many new words. These factors make them feel bored in learning to read.

* *Question 6: How often do you read diverse English documents such as Internet news, print newspapers, story books and comics in English, etc. to improve your reading skills?*

Figure 11: How often do you read diverse English documents such as Internet news, print newspapers, story books and comics in English, etc. to improve your reading skills?

From the chart above it shows the fact that the percentage of students who always or often read documents, English news accounts for only 10% and 26.67%, and half of them are only double. when reading English documents (50%). Of which 6.67% of respondents rarely read English documents, 6.67% of people said they never read documents in English. If students do not have the habit of reading documents, news on the internet, books, their vocabulary and sentence structure will be limited when reading English. However, first-year students majoring in English at HUFU don't seem to be paying attention to reading English materials from various sources. It is this low frequency of reading that makes it difficult for them to learn to read English.

4.2 Data analysis comes from external factors

* *Question 7: Are you exposed to English through a variety of sources such as TV shows, movies, cartoons, the internet, music in English, or interacting with English speakers?*

Figure 12 Are you exposed to English through a variety of sources such as TV shows, movies, cartoons, the internet, music in English, or interacting with English speakers?

According to the survey results of question 7 in the questionnaire, the percentage of students self-aware of learning English is higher. More than half of the students who are asked frequently or always practice English through different ways, however, nearly half of them have not found a way to study for themselves.

Currently, most of the student's recreational activities are mainly through foreign television programs, movies, internet or foreign music. Although students have access to a variety of sources to learn reading skills, the current reality is that they do not take advantage of these facilities for learning, but often focus on entertainment purposes. Useful tools that become useless in supporting their reading skills.

* Question 8: How do you feel about the teaching method of reading teachers?

Figure 13: How do you feel about the teaching method of reading teachers?

According to the chart above, nearly half of the students found the teacher's teaching method (47%), and 40% of the male respondents felt that the teacher was teaching at a normal level, neither interesting nor boring. 7% of the respondents feel their teacher's teaching method is boring.

Teaching methods for reading have been an important factor to improve students' reading skills, the more attractive the teacher's method is, the more motivated students are to read and vice versa.

* Question 9: What do you think of the textbooks and curriculum that are being used to teach reading skills at HUF1?

* Question 10: What do you think of the extra reading materials given by your teacher to improve your reading skills in class and at home?

Figure 14: What do you think of the textbooks and curriculum that are being used to teach reading skills at HUF1?

Figure 15 What do you think of the extra reading materials given by your teacher to improve your reading skills in class and at home?

The two charts above show the impact of books, curriculum, and further reading materials on students' reading skills. The results showed that the percentage of students found it interesting (30%) and found the material easy to learn (7%), with 56.67% of respondents saying the material was right for them. The rest admit that textbooks and curriculum, additional reading materials have become boring and difficult for them. This suggests that if the reading material is too confusing, it will make students lazy to learn to read. This makes learning to read ineffective.

In short, the difficulties in reading skills of first-year students majoring in English language at HUFU come from many different factors such as: weakness of the learners and external factors, learning environment. Due to personal factors, limited English reading ability, students do not spend much time learning to read, not learning new words as well as reading documents and news on the internet in English makes vocabulary lacking.

5. Discussion

**Research question 1: What are the difficulties in learning to read by first-year English language students at HUFU?*

Causes of reading difficulties of first-year students majoring in English language at HUFU include many different factors from causes of learners and external factors, learning environment. In terms of the reason why it is from the learners themselves, it is clear that students only have access to basic English for a few years, leading to students' limited English reading ability and that is one of the factors that makes reading skills difficult. Moreover, students do not spend much time on learning to read and they never learn new words nor read documents, news on the internet, stories or comics in English, because of the fact that the vocabulary is so limited that they cannot understand the content in English reading text. In addition, more the learner are lazy, the less they will be able to read. Moreover, students have good contact with foreign television programs, movies, cartoons, ... to learn reading skills. However, they don't take advantage of these facilities to study, mainly for entertainment. Therefore, these useful tools become useless in supporting their research in general and their reading skills in particular. In addition, they do not know how to apply reading strategies to deal with reading text. This leads to a boring situation in the reading process causing passive, positive psychology as well as difficult to absorb information in reading text. With regard to contextual causes, additional reading material does not seem simple to the learner and the teaching method employed by the teacher does not attract the attention of the student. These factors make reading time ineffective and lead to students having difficulty learning reading skills.

** Research question 2: What is the solution for first-year English language students at HUFU to overcome reading difficulties?*

To improve the writer's reading skills, the proposed solution for English language first-year students at HUFU is to develop a science reading strategy that is appropriate for themselves.

The first is that before reading, students should take steps to prepare, the first is to use their knowledge to think about the subject of the material to be read, the second is to make judgments about the probable content of the documents, the third is to preview the text by skimming and scanning to understand the overall meaning of the documents.

After reading, students need to list ideas, contents, information in the documents, relate what they have learned and read with their own experiences and knowledge, clarify the content of the text based on my understanding. Constantly expand your understanding.

Moreover, to make reading easier and more enjoyable. Foreign TV shows, movies and cartoons are good options for students. Free time because these tools help them have more English vocabulary and sentence structure. In addition, words and phrases are often repeated with vividness, which will help learners to remember new words longer.

On the other hand, teaching methods of reading teachers are also an important factor to improve students' reading skills. First, teachers must help students understand the importance of reading English. The lectures must be suitable for all students, inspiring students to study.

When students have knowledge gaps, teachers must have plans to supplement knowledge for students.

6. Conclusion

This research has been carried out in accordance with the concept to help first-year students majoring in English language at HUFU identify their difficulties in reading skills, at the same time, the researcher also offers some solutions for both students and teachers to overcome difficulties in students' reading skills.

Based on the findings and explanations in data analysis, the following conclusions can be drawn. Students who have difficulty in reading are rooted in both learners' personal and external factors, learning environment. Regarding personal factors, students spend too little time learning to read. In addition, they never learn new words and do not even have the habit of reading documents, news on the internet, stories or comics in English. Moreover, students have good access to foreign television programs, movies, cartoons, ... to learn reading skills. However, they don't make full use of these facilities to study, but to entertain. Besides, they do not know how to apply reading strategies in word processing for reading. Reducing contextual factors, teaching methods, and additional reading materials are too difficult for learners to understand. As a result, the students

displayed their rebellious behavior. These factors make reading time inefficient and lead to many problems for students in learning reading skills.

All of the individual and contextual factors are considered to inspire the researcher to come up with some useful solutions to reading the difficulties faced by first-year students majoring in English language at HUFU.

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